

IOT BASED SOLAR POWERED AIR MONITORING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This paper is about fabricating an air purifier system which is powered by solar energy and testing the effectiveness of the system to curb the air pollution. The focus is on extracting the suspended particulate matter from the air which are the major contributors in the pollution of air in many urban cities. It works on a nonconventional method and intends to achieve best possible air purification results using eco-friendly and economical method. It works on the basic principle of adhesion of the suspended particles in the air with the liquid and settles down due to being heavier than air and gets separated from the air helping us to achieve better air quality index. It works on the basic principle of adhesion of the suspended particles in the air with the liquid and settles down due to being heavier than air and gets separated from the air helping us to achieve better air quality index. This air purifier uses various processes like filtering large dirt particles on the first pre-filter, then capturing dust particles and smoke molecules at the bottom HEPA-filter and uses Carbon-filter to capture micro-particles produces clean purified air. The analysis and results conclude that the Air Purifier can produce 96 percent of clean air and can run up to 14 hours a day by a solar-powered system.

Keywords:

Introduction

As our project is based on IoT, let us throw some light on the topic of IoT itself. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a system of interrelated computing devices, mechanical and digital machines, objects, animals, or people that are provided with unique identifiers (UIDs) and the ability to transfer data over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction. So, we are making solar powered air purifier, which runs on solar energy without use of filters and works for longer duration than others. It uses components like solar panel, fan, converter, pump, etc. Now days, pollution in any form makes the world to be in a challenging situation. Most of the contamination comes as result from vehicle and civil construction areas, gases like Carbon-dioxide, earth dust, air particulates, abnormal gases, dusty area, etc. All the produce health issues when respired. The contaminated particles and air should be cleaned to reduce the respiratory from inhalation of the air. The respiratory organ may be produced to progression of sicknesses like asthma attack, etc. Bigger earth particles square-up a measure for significant material among these and the air in the surrounding will need a purification process as to the standard levels of pure air. Even though these measures undergo multiple processes of air track arrangement that square measure out there in market anyway none of them square measure sufficiently spare to convey its working intensity. Pollution has rocked the world with skyrocketing pollution levels.

As we know that air pollution level in cities is very high. Most of pollution come as by product from vehicle and construction of buildings, these are in form of particulate matter which are like methane, carbon dioxide, dust particulate etc. These create a lot of health problems like respiratory illness, decreased lung functions, development of diseases like asthma etc. Larger dust particles are major particulate among these and if its air quality value is down too minimum then air has very improved quality in which all type of living things can breathe easily. Although there are many types of air purifier

that are available in market but none of them are sufficient to deliver its working efficiency in public places like bus stand, near hospitals, traffic signals etc. Many institutes are also not able to afford these because of high cost and installation cost. Government organizations have very low budget for air purifier like extra expenditure.

So, it is advisable to develop such air purifier which can cost less and are highly efficient. Though the long-term solution to the pollution problem lies in finding and minimizing pollution sources, we need to bring the current pollution levels under control by the time. The best way of controlling pollution is by using air purifiers. But regular indoor air purifiers are small low power devices that don't possess enough purifying capability needed for outdoor spaces. Along with this there is also an issue of power supply in outdoor machines. So here we design a heavy-duty outdoor air purifier that is made for outdoor purification along and powered by solar panels, so it is energy independent. Our solar air purifier consists of a heavy-duty suction fan that pulls air from the bottom of the purifier through a layer of HEPA and Carbon filters for elimination of PM 10 PM 2.5 pollutants as well as gases.

The purifier uses 2-layer purification, the first one being HEPA layer and second and active carbon filter. The

combination of these 2 filters leads to dual filtration using a centrifugal air force to suck large amount of air and purify it of dust particles. Now this suction fan is used to suck out air using high power centrifugal force and blowing out fresh air from the top. The system also includes an air quality sensor and display to display the current air quality. We now use a solar panel for the power supply. The panel is used to supply electricity to battery which in turn powers the motor to run the suction fan.

Swati Jha, Pranit Murlidhar Nakade, Meghraj Prashant Nazare- In this paper we are dealing with the measurement of Air Quality using MQ135 sensor along with Carbon Monoxide CO using MQ7 sensor and also provides warning if level of toxic gases rises to a certain dangerous or hazardous level. Nowadays measuring Air Quality Index helps us in getting aware about our polluted environment and inspires us to save it for our future generations. This also warns us that we may not be able to live a healthy life if the air quality is poor.

Sahapong Somwong, Tanakorn Intasuth, Kritisada puangsuwan- This article describes a system that can detect and display various air pollution values that occur within a community in order to monitor and warn of air quality to the people in the community to effectively protect their health.

Based on the need for and importance of air quality monitoring system, our work is to develop a low cost simple air quality monitoring system was successfully demonstrated and the details are highlighted in this paper.

Materials and Methods

As urbanization causes the growth of suburban communities, the existing transportation infrastructure dependent on fossil fuels must expand. An increase in vehicle use gives rise to an increase in traffic-related pollutant emissions. According to science, the six common air pollutants are particulate matter, ground-level ozone, carbon monoxide, sulfur oxides, nitrogen oxides, and lead. These are called the criteria pollutants and thus are required to be measured to tell us how healthy the air is to breathe. Vehicular emissions contribute carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, and nitrogen oxides to air pollution. The current pollution measurement methodology uses expensive equipment at fixed locations or dedicated mobile equipment. The raw data obtained in this manner is used to further extrapolate the

extent and concentration of pollution through dispersion models. This is a coarse-grained system where the pollution measurements are few and far in-between. Widespread deployment of this measurement paradigm is constrained by its prohibitive cost. In addition, it is desirable to have access to real-time measurements to be able to quickly analyse and identify alarming levels of pollutants. Currently, access to such data is limited if not absent. It is available to and discernable by only a few who are well informed on the subject of pollution.

The different parts involved in the systems are mentioned below:

2.1 SOLAR PANEL: -

A solar panel is a device that converts sunlight into electricity by using photovoltaic (PV) cells. PV cells are made of materials that produce excited electrons when exposed to light. The electrons flow through a circuit and produce direct current (DC) electricity, which can be used to power various devices or be stored in batteries. Solar panels are also known as solar cell panels, solar electric panels, or PV modules.

Solar panels are usually arranged in groups called arrays or systems. A photovoltaic system consists of one or more solar panels, an inverter that converts DC electricity to alternating current (AC) electricity, and sometimes other components such as controllers, meters, and trackers. Most panels are in solar farms, which supply the electricity grid as can some rooftop solar.

Some advantages of solar panels are that they use a renewable and clean source of energy, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and lower electricity bills. Some disadvantages are that they depend on the availability and intensity of sunlight, require cleaning, and have high initial costs. Solar panels are widely used for residential, commercial, and industrial purposes, as well as in space, often together with batteries.

2.2 BATTERY: -

A device containing an electric cell or a series of electric cells storing energy that can be converted into electrical power. A battery can be defined as an electrochemical device (consisting of one or more electrochemical cells) which can be charged with an electric current and discharged whenever required. Batteries are usually devices that are made up of multiple electrochemical cells that are connected to external inputs and outputs.

Batteries are widely employed to power small electric devices such as mobile phones, remotes, and flashlights. Historically, the 'term' battery has always been used to refer to the combination of two or more electrochemical cells. However, the modern definition of the term 'battery' is believed to accommodate devices that only feature a single cell.

2.3 ARDUINO: -

Arduino is an open-source electronics platform based on easy-to-use hardware and software. Arduino boards are able to read inputs - light on a sensor, a finger on a button, or a Twitter message - and turn it into an output - activating a motor, turning on an LED, publishing something online. You can tell your board what to do by sending a set of instructions to the microcontroller on the board. To do so you use the Arduino programming language (based on Wiring), and the Arduino Software (IDE), based on Processing.

Over the years Arduino has been the brain of thousands of projects, from everyday objects to complex scientific instruments. A worldwide community of makers - students, hobbyists, artists, programmers, and professionals - has gathered around this open-source platform, their contributions have added up to an incredible amount of accessible knowledge that can be of great help to novices and experts alike.

Arduino was born at the Ivrea Interaction Design Institute as an easy tool for fast prototyping, aimed at students without a background in electronics and programming. As soon as it reached a wider community, the Arduino board started changing to adapt to new needs and challenges, differentiating its offer from simple 8-bit boards to products for IoT applications, wearable, 3D printing, and embedded environments.

2.4 MQ135 SENSOR: -

Sensitive material of MQ135 gas sensor is SnO₂, which with lower conductivity in clean air. When target pollution gas exists, the sensor's conductivity gets higher along with the gas concentration rising. Users can convert the change of conductivity to correspond output signal of gas concentration through a simple circuit.

MQ135 gas sensor has high sensitivity to ammonia gas, sulfide, benzene series steam, also can monitor smoke and other toxic gases well. It can detect kinds of toxic gases and is a kind of low-cost sensor for kinds of applications.

2.5 MQ7 GAS SENSOR: -

The MQ7 is a simple-to-use Carbon Monoxide (CO) sensor suitable for sensing CO concentrations in the air. It can detect CO-gas concentrations anywhere from 20 to 2000ppm. MQ7 is a high sensitivity to carbon monoxide and stable and long-life span.

Sensitive material of MQ-7 gas sensor is SnO₂, which with lower conductivity in clean air. It make detection by method of cycle high and coldness, and detect CO when coldness (heated by 1.5V). The sensor's conductivity is higher alongside the gas concentration rising. When high temperature (heated by 5.0V), it cleans the other gases adsorbed under low temperature. Please use simple electro circuit, Convert change of conductivity to correspond output signal of gas concentration.

MQ-7 gas sensor has high sensitivity to Carbon Monoxide. The sensor could be used to detect different gases contains CO, it is with low cost and suitable for different application. This semiconductor gas sensor detects the presence of Carbon Monoxide at concentrations from 10 to 10,000 ppm. The sensor's simple analog voltage interface requires only one analog input pin from your microcontroller. Sensitive material of MQ-7 gas sensor is SnO₂, which with lower conductivity in clean air. It make detection by method of cycle high and coldness, and detect CO when coldness (heated by 1.5V). ... When high temperature (heated by 5.0V), it cleans the other gases adsorbed under low temperature.

This carbon monoxide gas (CO) gas sensor detects the concentrations of CO within the air and outputs its reading as an analog voltage. The sensor can measure concentrations of 10 to 10,000 ppm. The sensor can operate at temperatures from -10 to 50°C and consumes but 150 mA at 5 V. Connecting five volts across the heating (H) pins keeps the sensor hot enough to function correctly. Connecting five volts at either the A or B pins causes the sensor to emit an analog voltage on the other pins. A resistive load between the output pins and ground sets the sensitivity of the detector. The resistive load should be calibrated for your particular application using the equations within the datasheet, but an honest starting value for the resistor is 10 kΩ.

2.6 RELAY: -

A relay is an electrically operated switch. It consists of a set of input terminals for a single or multiple control signals, and a set of operating contact terminals. The switch may have any number of contacts in multiple contact forms, such as make contacts, break contacts, or combinations thereof.

Relays are used where it is necessary to control a circuit by an independent low-power signal, or where several circuits must be controlled by one signal. Relays were first used in long-distance telegraph circuits as signal repeaters: they refresh the signal coming in from one circuit by transmitting it on another circuit. Relays were used extensively in telephone exchanges and early computers to perform logical operations.

The traditional electromechanical form of a relay uses an electromagnet to close or open the contacts, but relays using other operating principles have also been invented, such as in solid-state relays which use semiconductor properties for control without relying on moving parts. Relays with calibrated operating characteristics and sometimes multiple operating coils are used to protect electrical circuits from overload or faults; in modern electric power systems these functions are performed by digital instruments still called protective relays or safety relays.

Latching relays require only a single pulse of control power to operate the switch persistently. Another

pulse applied to a second set of control terminals, or a pulse with opposite polarity, resets the switch, while repeated pulses of the same kind have no effects. Magnetic latching relays are useful in applications when interrupted power should not affect the circuits that the relay is controlling.

2.7 HEPA FILTER: -

Filters meeting the HEPA standard must satisfy certain levels of efficiency. Common standards require that a HEPA air filter must remove—from the air that passes through—at least 99.95% A HEPA filter is also able to capture floor dust which contains bacteroidia, clostridia, and bacilli. HEPA was commercialized in the 1950s, and the original term became a registered trademark and later a generic trademark for highly efficient filters. HEPA filters are used in applications that require contamination control, such as the manufacturing of hard disk drives, medical devices, semiconductors, nuclear, food and pharmaceutical products, as well as in hospitals, homes, and vehicles.

HEPA filters are composed of a mat of randomly arranged fibers. The fibers are typically composed of polypropylene or fiberglass with diameters between 0.5 and 2.0 micrometers. Most of the time, these filters are composed of tangled bundles of fine fibers. These fibers create a narrow convoluted pathway through which air passes. When the largest particles are passing through this pathway, the bundles of fibers behave like a kitchen sieve which physically blocks the particles from passing through. However, when smaller particles pass with the air, as the air twists and turns, the smaller particles cannot keep up with the motion of the air and thus they collide with the fibers. The smallest particles have very little inertia and they always move around the air molecules like they are bombarded by these molecules (Brownian motion). Because of their movement, they end up crashing into the fibers. Key factors affecting its functions are fiber diameter, filter thickness, and

2.8 CARBON FILTER: -

Carbon filtering works by adsorption, in which pollutants in the fluid to be treated are trapped inside the pore structure[1] of a carbon substrate. The substrate is made of many carbon granules, each of which is itself highly porous. As a result, the substrate has a large surface area within which contaminants can be trapped. Activated carbon is typically used in filters, as it has been treated to have a much higher surface area than non treated carbon. One gram of activated carbon has a surface area in excess of 3,000 m² (32,000 sq ft).

Carbon filtering is commonly used for water purification, air filtering and industrial gas processing, for example the removal of siloxanes and hydrogen sulfide from biogas. It is also used in a number of other applications, including respirator masks, the purification of sugarcane, some methods of coffee decaffeination, and in the recovery of precious metals, especially gold. It is also used in cigarette filters and in the EVAP used in cars.

Each carbon filter is typically given a micron rating that specifies the size of particle which the filter can remove from a fluid. Typical particle sizes which can be removed by carbon filters range from 0.5 to 50 μm . The efficacy of a carbon filter depends not only on its particle size, but also on the rate of flow of fluid through the filter. For example, if a fluid is allowed to flow through the filter at a slower rate, the contaminants will be exposed to the filter media for a longer amount of time, which will tend to result in fewer impurities.

2.9 PUMP: -

A pump is a device that moves fluids (liquids or gases), or sometimes slurries, by mechanical action, typically converted from electrical energy into hydraulic energy.

Mechanical pumps serve in a wide range of applications such as pumping water from wells, aquarium filtering, pond filtering and aeration, in the car industry for water-cooling and fuel injection, in the energy industry for pumping oil and natural gas or for operating cooling towers and other components of heating, ventilation and air conditioning systems. In the medical industry, pumps are used for biochemical processes in developing and manufacturing medicine, and as artificial replacements for body parts, in particular the artificial heart and penile prosthesis.

When a pump contains two or more pump mechanisms with fluid being directed to flow through them in series, it is called a multi-stage pump. Terms such as two-stage or double-stage may be used to specifically describe the number of stages. A pump that does not fit this description is simply a single-stage pump in contrast.

In biology, many different types of chemical and biomechanical pumps have evolved; biomimicry is sometimes used in developing new types of mechanical pumps.

Experimental Setup

Figure 1 The working model of Air quality monitoring and supply system

Results and Discussions:

Solar Panel selection

The total power required=power of fan +power of pump + extra power for storage in battery

Purification of Air Formulae

Moisture content = [AQI of fan +pump + incense stick]-[AQI of fan +pump]

Amount of purification = AQI of incense stick – moisture content

Purification Percentage = [(reduction of AQI/AQI of incense stick) * 100]

Theoretical background calculation

- Time taken to charge a 12V/7.5Ah battery from 5W Solar panel:
- Solar panel and components specifications:
- 12 volt/7Ah battery
- 5-watt solar panel

- solar charge controller in order
- To estimate charge controller's maximum output:
 $T = Ah/A = 5w/12v = 0.416A$
- Taking power losses (25%) and efficiency of solar-charge controller $\gt 75\% * 0.416A (1 - (25/100)) * (75/100) = 0.1755$ amperes

Taking Lead-Acid battery efficiency:

$$85\% * 7.5Ah * (1 / (85 / 100)) = 7.5Ah$$

Time to charge entire battery approximately if it charges 2A per hour:

$$7.5Ah / 2A = 3.7 \text{ hrs.}$$

Considering, most of the charge controllers have absorption charging time 2 hrs.

$$3.7 \text{ hrs.} + 2 \text{ hrs.} = 5.7 \text{ hrs.} (\sim 6 \text{ hrs.})$$

Therefore, it will take around 6 hrs. to charge the 12V/7.5Ah battery entirely.

Time taken by 0.5A Air Purifier Motor Fan to discharge 12V/7Ah battery:

To calculate the No. of hrs., a motor of 0.18-amp motor that runs on

7.5Ah battery, if the battery is fully charged:

$$7.5Ah / 0.18 = 40h$$

So, the Solar Powered Air Purifier System can run approximately up to 40 hrs. from 7.5Ah battery, if the battery is fully charged $\gt$ Calculating Air Quality Percentage:

Assuming normal smoke conditions, the MQ135 sensor provides reading from 0 to 1300 PPM (for ammonia or benzene gases - 0 to 900 PPM) $\gt$ Sensor Percentage = (Air Quality Reading * 100) / 1300

CONCLUSIONS:

Now we have seen that how efficient is SOLAR POWERED AIR PURIFIER than other type of device available in market. It also very economical and do not have to replace any component quickly. It reduces particulate level to satisfactory position where a person does not need to worry about pollution related problems. A pure and clean air is right of a human being and all other living creatures on this earth and this project is a small effort from our side to give all their right.

Also in future, modifications can be made to improve working efficiency without effecting setup. This research proposed a smart air pollution monitoring system that constantly keeps track of air quality in an area and displays the air quality measured on an LCD screen the system helps to create awareness of the Quality of air that one breathes daily. This monitoring device can deliver real-time.

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